

Application of PSO for optimal coordination of directional over-current relays in distribution system with distributed renewable energy sources

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ABSTRACT

The use of Distributed Renewable Energy Sources in the electrical network has expanded greatly. But, integration of these resources into distribution systems caused more problems in protection related issues such as mis-coordination, and changes the direction and value of fault currents. When connecting new D-RES to electrical power distribution networks, it is required to re-coordinate Directional Over-Current Relays (DOC-Relays) to ensure the continuity of the power transmission when the short circuits take place. This work presented a Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm to determine two independent variables called Pickup current (I_p) and Time Dial Setting (TDS) for optimal setting of relays. From analysis result, the impacts of RES location in the distribution system on DOCRs had been observed on the optimal relays settings.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Distributed renewable energy generation is small power-generating unit clubbed with modern technologies and present diverse challenges while integrating with utility grid. Most of the distributed renewable energy sources (D-RESs) shall be located near load centre on distribution grid. D-RES introduces negative effects on system operation. One of the negative impacts is relay coordination [1]. The integration of distributed renewable energy sources (D-RES) on the electrical network contains many advantages. However, the result of introducing these energies in the network will change the value and direction of energy flow as well as short-circuit current levels in different points. Several factors may lead to the effects of RES energies on protection devices, including the type of technology, capacitance and the position in the network [2].

The authors in [3], proposed a dual simplex method to find the setting of TDS while keeping constant values of I_p in modified IEEE 33-bus with installing the D-RES. In the present article, a Particle swarm optimization is proposed to find out the new setting for both TDS and I_p of relays with respect to various constraints in the presence of two D-RES.

2. DIRECTIONAL OVER-CURRENT RELAYS

For optimal coordination of DOC Relays, it is necessary to determine the optimal values of TDS and IP of each relay in the system, this optimization of TDS and IP for minimize the operating time of the primary relays. The tripping time equation of DOC Relay is a non-linear equation, Depending on the fault current and both TDS and IP settings. Thus, the relay tripping time equation for DOC Relay is given by (1) [4], [5].

$$T_{ot} = TDS \times \frac{0,14}{\left(\frac{I_f}{KCT \times I_p}\right)^{0,02} - 1} \quad (1)$$

Where, KCT is the current transformer ratio.

The pickup value is the minimum value of the current for which the relay operates. The operating time (T_{ot}) of the relay is defined by the TDS for each current value. The limits on the TDS can be presented as (2)

$$TDS_i^{min} \leq TDS_i \leq TDS_i^{max} \quad (2)$$

The TDS are assumed to vary between 0.05 and 1.2.

$$I_{Pi}^{min} \leq I_{Pi} \leq I_{Pi}^{max} \quad (3)$$

The pickup current setting I_p are assumed to vary between 0.25 and 2.5 with step 0.25

When a fault occurs, there must be primary protection for isolat as soon as possible to reduce the isolated area as much as possible, and in the case of primary relay, other relay should be protected as backup protection to assure the requirement of selectivity. In order to satisfy selective requirements, you must add the following limitation [6], [7].

$$T_{back-up}^{FI} - T_{primary}^{FI} \leq CTI \quad (4)$$

$$T_j^{FI} - T_i^{FI} \leq CTI \quad (5)$$

Where

T_j^{FI} is the tripping time of jth backup relay;

T_i^{FI} is the tripping times of ith primary relay.

The CTI is the minimum time gap in operation between the primary and its backup relay, is usually selected between 0.2 s and 0.5 s [4], [7], [8]. The CTI is set to a desired value of 0.3 sec.

3. IMPLEMENTATION OF PROPOSED PSO ALGORITHM ON THE COORDINATION PROBLEM

The Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), which has gained rapid popularity as an efficient optimization technique, is relatively a recent heuristic introduced by Eberhart and Kennedy [9]. The various steps involved in the implementation of PSO to the DOCRs problem with 64 decisions variables are:

Step1. Input the data of 33 IEEE distribution test system for calculate the power flow and current

Step2. Define population size (50), no of iteration (=500), assume suitable values of PSO parameters

Step3. Initial searching points and velocities are randomly generated within their limits. Pbest is set to each initial searching point. The best-evaluated values among individual best (P^{best}) are set to global best (g^{best}).

Step4. New velocities are calculated using the equation (9).

Step5. Evaluate the fitness values for new searching point. If evaluated values of each agent is better than previous Pbest then set to Pbest. If the best Pbest is better than best gbest then set to gbest.

Step6. If the maximum iteration is reached stop the process otherwise go to step3.

The summation of tripping times of all primary relays is known as objective function (OF). Conventionally, the optimal coordination problem determines two parameters, that is, the pickup current setting I_p and the time dial setting TDS. The OF is given by:

$$OF = \min \sum_{i=1}^N t_{il} \quad (6)$$

Where: OF is the objective function in sec,

t_{ij} is the operating time of the i th relay,
 N is the total DOCRs in the system.

The two variables in the objective function are TDS and I_p . By minimizing both the TDS and I_p we can able to minimize the tripping time of the primary relays and satisfying the CTI.

3.1. Goal of Study

This work, presented the PSO algorithm to find the optimal CTI of DOC Relays. The proposed algorithm was evaluated using IEEE 33-bus system in presence of two D-RESs. The main contributions of this paper are using the optimization technique to find optimal relay settings, solve the non-linear coordination problem of DOC Relays with the system changed topology.

4. CASE STUDIES

In this paper IEEE 33-bus radial distribution feeder is considered to optimal pair of DOC Relays in presence of two emplacements of D-RES. The operating voltage is 12.66 kV. DOC Relays are used in the system to protect the feeder in case of three phase faults. The IEEE 33-bus system is presented in Figure 1 [10], [11]. The model is simulated in MATLAB software without and with Renewable Energy Sources to calculate the optimal setting of DOCRs using PSO method under system changes. The program is implemented for two emplacements of Renewable Energy Sources. Three phase Faults are generated on each bus.

Figure 1. Power distribution system of the IEEE 33-bus system under study

4.1. Impact of the D-RES on the short circuit level

From a power perspective, the integration of a new D-RES into the distribution networks will increase the power of the network. Thus the new source will be modeled in such a way as to take only its current contribution in the event of a short circuit. The electrical network, of which we will determine the different short circuit currents without (and with) D-RES, has a radial architecture Figure 1, and we take a part of this network for the calculations of short circuit currents, as show in Figure 2.

Figure. 2. Simple distribution network with RES

The current in the fault point will be the sum of the short circuit current without D-RES and the short circuit current injected into the network only by the D-RES, is given by (7)

$$I_{cc} = I_{cc}^{grid} + I_{cc}^{D-RES} \tag{7}$$

The direct impedance seen between the bar (11) and the earth is (8)

$$Z_{d-cc}^{D-RES} = Z_{d-cc}^{D-RES} + jX_{cc}^{D-RES} + Z_{d-Line2} \tag{8}$$

Implies that (9), (10), (11).

$$I_a^{D-RES} = \frac{V_d^p}{Z_{d-cc}^{D-RES} + jX_{cc}^{D-RES} + Z_{d-Line2}} \tag{9}$$

$$I_b^{D-RES} = a^2 \cdot \frac{V_d^p}{Z_{d-cc}^{D-RES} + jX_{cc}^{D-RES} + Z_{d-Line2}} \tag{10}$$

$$I_c^{D-RES} = a \cdot \frac{V_d^p}{Z_{d-cc}^{D-RES} + jX_{cc}^{D-RES} + Z_{d-Line2}} \tag{11}$$

We find the fault current is (12), (13), and (14).

$$I_a = \frac{V_d^p}{Z_{d-cc} + Z_{d-Line1} + Z_{d-Line2}} + \frac{V_d^p}{Z_{d-cc}^{D-RES} + jX_{cc}^{D-RES} + Z_{d-Line2}} \tag{12}$$

$$I_b = a^2 \cdot \left[\frac{V_d^p}{Z_{d-cc} + Z_{d-Line1} + Z_{d-Line2}} + \frac{V_d^p}{Z_{d-cc}^{D-RES} + jX_{cc}^{D-RES} + Z_{d-Line2}} \right] \tag{13}$$

$$I_c = a \cdot \left[\frac{V_d^p}{Z_{d-cc} + Z_{d-Line1} + Z_{d-Line2}} + \frac{V_d^p}{Z_{d-cc}^{D-RES} + jX_{cc}^{D-RES} + Z_{d-Line2}} \right] \tag{14}$$

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two locations are chosen for installing the D-RES in the distribution system; to illustrate the effects of D-RES insertions on the setting of Relays. A minimum relay tripping time is the main goal of setting of relays. Also the CTI is satisfied (i.e., $CTI \geq 0.3$). Table 1 shows the optimal results of TDSs in presence of D-RES installation in the 33-bus distribution system. Table 2 shows the optimal results of I_{ps} in presence of D-RES.

Table 1. Setting values of relais TDS

Relays	Setting of TDS	
	Without D-RES	With D-RES
TDS ₁	0.5000	0.5000
TDS ₂	0.3500	0.3500
TDS ₃	0.3400	0.3400
TDS ₄	0.3300	0.3300
TDS ₅	0.3400	0.3000
TDS ₆	0.3500	0.3500
TDS ₇	0.2700	0.2700
TDS ₈	0.2400	0.2000
TDS ₉	0.3100	0.3800
TDS ₁₀	0.4600	0.5700
TDS ₁₁	0.4200	0.5200
TDS ₁₂	0.3000	0.4000
TDS ₁₃	0.3400	0.4500

Table 2. Setting values of relais Ip

Relays	Setting of Ip	
	Without D-RES	With D-RES
Ip ₁	0.7300	0.7300
Ip ₂	0.7500	0.7500
Ip ₃	1.0400	1.0400
Ip ₄	0.8100	0.8100
Ip ₅	0.3500	0.5000
Ip ₆	0.3500	0.3500
Ip ₇	1.0700	1.0700
Ip ₈	1.0100	1.2000
Ip ₉	0.3600	0.3600
Ip ₁₀	0.5200	0.5200
Ip ₁₁	0.5600	0.5300
Ip ₁₂	0.5400	0.5100
Ip ₁₃	0.5600	0.5500

Table 1. Setting values of relais TDS (*Continued*)

Relays	Setting of TDS	
	Without D-RES	With D-RES
TDS ₁₄	0.3700	0.4100
TDS ₁₅	0.3600	0.4500
TDS ₁₆	0.3000	0.3900
TDS ₁₇	0.3200	0.4500
TDS ₁₈	0.4000	0.0700
TDS ₁₉	0.2600	0.1700
TDS ₂₀	0.3500	0.3700
TDS ₂₁	0.3200	0.3300
TDS ₂₂	0.3300	0.0900
TDS ₂₃	0.2900	0.0500
TDS ₂₄	0.2800	0.3200
TDS ₂₅	0.4300	0.4000
TDS ₂₆	0.4400	0.3800
TDS ₂₇	0.3200	0.2600
TDS ₂₈	0.3300	0.2700
TDS ₂₉	0.3400	0.3700
TDS ₃₀	0.2600	0.2800
TDS ₃₁	0.3300	0.3500
TDS ₃₂	0.4200	0.4400

Table 2. Setting values of relais Ip (*Continued*)

Relays	Setting of Ip	
	Without D-RES	With D-RES
Ip ₁₄	0.5200	1.0500
Ip ₁₅	0.5300	0.5000
Ip ₁₆	0.5000	0.5300
Ip ₁₇	0.8300	0.5300
Ip ₁₈	1.2200	1.2300
Ip ₁₉	1.0300	1.0000
Ip ₂₀	0.5000	0.5200
Ip ₂₁	0.5500	0.5100
Ip ₂₂	0.9800	1.0300
Ip ₂₃	1.0200	1.0200
Ip ₂₄	1.0100	0.9800
Ip ₂₅	0.5200	0.7500
Ip ₂₆	0.5500	0.5200
Ip ₂₇	0.5700	0.5100
Ip ₂₈	0.5200	0.5600
Ip ₂₉	0.7200	0.7400
Ip ₃₀	1.5600	1.6000
Ip ₃₁	1.0900	1.1300
Ip ₃₂	0.5100	0.5200

The results obtained after the study from the proposed PSO Algorithm of the impact of D-RES on the DOC-Relays settings are displayed in Tables 1 and 2. By examining the results obtained, it can be said that D-RES increased the values of short circuit currents at the fault point. This increase will be reflected in the reduced operating time for protection before damage to the equipment that makes up the electrical network.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper the authors presented the Particle Swarm Optimization method to explain and visualize the influence of D-RES on the protection settings of DOC Relays in the test system. The result of using PSO algorithm on an IEEE 33-bus is compared in two cases with and without D-RES. From analysis result, the impacts of D-RES location in the distribution system had been observed on the optimal relays settings. The results show the optimal settings of DOC-relays for eliminate the three fault currents.

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